

RETHINKING DATA REQUIREMENTS FOR THE RELIABILITY ASSESSMENT OF MEDIUM VOLTAGE CABLES

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ABSTRACT

The main aging and failure drivers of medium voltage cables are known. However, the distribution grid's enormous number of cables makes it difficult to determine the status of each cable section individually. Machine learning approaches to predict the reliability of medium voltage cables are promising, but often use non-standard features. As a result, it remains difficult to quantify the influence of each failure driver and evaluate correlations. Therefore, this work redefines the data requirements for data driven approaches of reliability assessment for medium voltage cables, by providing an overview of features to represent aging drivers. Furthermore, main data sources for Denmark are identified and merged to assess issues in data collection, availability, and combination. Finally, data management, and feature selection tasks are discussed to accurately employ the defined data requirements in future condition monitoring applications.

INTRODUCTION

To cope with emerging operational trends and challenges, distribution system operators (DSOs) seek to gain a deeper understanding about their components condition [1]. Through estimating probabilities of failure (PoF) DSOs can mitigate threats to severely aged assets and extend the lifespan of components under favourable conditions. Further, this enables to operate the grid more adaptably and risk-aware, foster renewable energy grid integration, optimise grid investments [2] and define right number and placement of sensors or automation equipment [3].

Industrial standards outline general data needs for reliability-centred maintenance and operation [4]. Moreover, research on aging drivers of distribution system (DS) components is available [5]. Additionally, the reliability of DSs has been subject to proposals for data-driven machine learning (ML) models [6].

However, data requirements to model the PoF of individual DS components are hardly described so far. In addition, it is unclear how to optimally collect and manage data. As a result, current approaches often use non-standard data.

Thus, a feature definition process becomes necessary, which quantifies the influence of each feature, identifies correlations, and enables the comparison of different methodologies. Although a feature definition is required for all DSs components, it is especially beneficial to define it for medium voltage (MV) cables (10kV, 15kV and 20kV). Because they are responsible for a big part of future DSs

Figure 1: Process to define, collect and use data for the failure prediction of medium voltage cables

investments [2]. Furthermore, unplanned interruptions in the Danish MV cable systems counted in 2021 for 45% of the System Average Duration Index (SAIDI) and 50% of the System Average Interruption Frequency Index (SAIFI). Additionally, the relatively high number of cables and historic failures facilitates the development of ML approaches to estimate reliability. Lastly, the MV cable network in Denmark contains Paper Isolated Lead Cover (PILC) cables, where replacement prioritisation strategies might be required in coming years, due to higher age distributions and failure probabilities (0.038 failure /km in 2021).

Consequently, as visualised in figure 1, this paper aims to contribute to the reliability assessment of MV cables, by:

1. Qualitatively define the features to model failure drivers, based on existing standards and literature
2. List main data sources of the defined features for Denmark
3. Evaluates challenges in terms of data collection, availability, quality, and combination
4. Provide an outlook on required feature selection processes and usages within ML models

STATE OF THE ART

Literature review

There exist several studies on aging mechanisms of MV cables. As an example, [5] discusses main ageing factors and associated ageing mechanisms. In Summary, main factors are either thermal, electrical, environmental, or mechanical. Thermal aging contains drivers such as

maximum, low, or high ambient temperature and temperature gradients or cycles. Electrical drivers derive from high (impulse) voltages, and deviations from operation frequency and currents. Aging due to gases, lubricants, water, humidity, soil type and condition, corrosive chemicals, and radiation are summarized as environmental drivers. Lastly, mechanical factors combine drivers such as bending, tension, compression, torsion, thermal-mechanical stress, and vibration. A general overview of the relation between aging factor, mechanisms, and effects of cable insulation system is also available [5]. For example, several temperature cycles (aging factor) can lead to multiple thermal expansion processes (aging mechanism) resulting in a loss of mechanical strength (aging effect).

Existing literature addresses that aging factors and mechanisms differ for paper isolated or extruded cables [7]. Some ageing mechanisms, such as ageing of metal sheaths, apply to both cable types. Others, such as insulation deterioration due to the development of water trees refer only to XLPE cables. This results in different feature requirements for modelling the reliability of the respective cable types. Previous research has also investigated several aging drivers in detail, such as the impact of lightning [8], environmental conditions [9], and stray current close to DC railway systems [10]. However, research on correlation between aging drivers and their contribution to aging of individual components is rather limited. Furthermore, recommendations on what data to collect to best represent ageing mechanisms are also hardly available.

Standard review

The need of data collection for reliability purposes is mentioned in several industry standards, such as in IEC TS 63060. However, to the authors' knowledge, there is no standardised collection of aging drivers for MV cables and their correlation and impact available today. Furthermore, the processes of data collection, management, and combination are not clearly defined. Although the standards examined partly mention costs of data collection, no link is made between benefits of features and their collection costs. Standards from other industry domains, such as petroleum and natural gas [11] provide a more detailed overview on data collection for reliability purposes and can serve as an orientation for assembling data for reliability studies. Main categories mentioned are equipment parameter, failure parameters and maintenance data. Lastly, there are several standards on cable operation, such as IEC 60287-2-1. As they often include operational failure and risk drivers, like loading limits, they are highly beneficial to establish data requirements. In [12] a common methodology to calculate asset health is provided, however it not sufficiently represents medium voltage cables.

DEFINITION OF DATA REQUIREMENTS

This chapter lists relevant features to link aging drivers on cable section and, based on this, defines data requirements for ML based reliability assessment of MV cables.

Failure data

Information about previous failures is essential to predict future failures [4]. However, full potential is only realised if failure reports are enriched with e.g., equipment or GIS information. Locations of failures can link to location-based failure drivers, such as soil type, while date and time of historic failures can link to other time-based failure drivers, such as climate. Moreover, the link to root data is beneficial, as it points to reliability behaviour of similar components in use. The grid situation during the failure, defined by loading, voltage, topology, etc., indicates electrical stress of the cable. Thus, also improves the ability to study the effects of failures from neighbouring components and enables system reliability studies. In summary, the following criteria are at least required: failure date [date], location [GIS], cause [category], topology, component category [kV], identifier [id], loading [MW], voltage [kV] and operation readings [I, V, P, Q].

Equipment data

Root information

Root data from currently or previously used cables is required, because the cable insulation, conductor material, number of cores, length, and cross-section behave differently in different environments and operating conditions. Whereas the cable location links to location-based drivers, such as soil type. As a result, the following root data parameters should at least be included: cable-id [id], operating voltage [kV], conductor material and insulation [category], length [km], number of conductors [number], conductor cross section [mm²], number of joints [number], cable location [GIS].

Date of cable installation and end of life

With increasing operating time, cables are longer exposed to external influences. Some external influences can therefore only be evaluated by cumulative observations, e.g., number of frost days, etc. Therefore, both installation date and end of operational life are needed to calculate the operating time. In some cases, manufacture and installation date might be different. In this case additional aging due to the storage period might become relevant. The authors of [7] distinguish between technical, strategic, and economic end of life of cables systems. Monitoring these can also improve the estimation of failure probabilities. In summary, at least the following features should be tracked: Installation date [date], manufacture date/year [date/year], end of life [date], reason for end of life [category].

Operational data

Electrical parameters

The cable operation can strongly influence ageing and failures. Load flow or state estimation calculations, based on e.g., smart meter readings, can assign electrical parameters to cables and failure reports, and thus represent operational states. Additionally, this enables to consider system perspectives, e.g., verify that components also suffer from neighboured component failures.

Information on the current and historical grid topology and switching positions are thus also required. In conclusion, the following electrical parameters should at least be tracked: maximum utilisation [%], mean utilisation [%], design voltage [kV], Time-series measurements [U, I; P, Q.], topology and switching positions.

Location-based features

There are a lot of location-based features that might represent aging drivers of medium voltage cables. The most important ones for investigation, from the authors perspective, are listed in the following.

Digging activities: Digging activities have been the second highest share of MV cable failures in Denmark in 2021, after material-based failures. Furthermore, it can be assumed that many of the material-based failures are correlated to previous digging activities. As ground movements, changes of the cable placement and damages to the cable itself might not lead to an instant failure but to accelerated aging.

Soil type and conditions: Previous research, such as [13], revealed, that soil type and conditions have a significant influence on the heat dissipation during the lifetime of DS cables. Additionally, probability of water ingress in the cable might correlate with the surrounded soil and groundwater depth. Salt in the ground can affect corrosivity. Thus, even the consideration of anaerobic soil conditions, might be justifiable, as they facilitate removal of nitrate, which is a salt that can affect corrosivity.

Climate data such as temperature (ambient, soil, etc.) or humidity, can be a source of temperature and mechanical stress, and thus lead to accelerated aging of cables [9]. Moreover, it can possess a high influence and/or correlation to other impact drivers, such as water ingress, partial discharge, loading or soil conditions. In combination with cable age, aggregated exposure to climate effects becomes also relevant. For example, the cumulated number of very cold days could give an indication of additional aging of underground cables, as the freezing and thawing of the surrounding soil can lead to additional mechanical stress [14].

Lightning data: One known sources of transient overvoltage are lightning strokes. These can have a negative impact on cables insulation, thus cause the insulation to spontaneously fail. Furthermore, earth strikes can cause significant potential gradients, which can increase soil stress around the impact spot. Even a disruptive discharge can occur between the place of impact and a nearby cable depending on the soil's dielectric strength. Lightning current can enter the cable surface through a channel formed when the field produced by lightning exceeds the soil's resistivity breaking point. [8] Among that, lightning strokes can also affect the polymer sheath of shielded cables and generated pinholes where water can enter the cables insulation. However, the maximum influence is expected at places without lightning protection systems.

Distance to roads: Previous research and operators in the electrical distribution network have noticed that ground movement caused by vibrations of traffic, can lead to mechanical stress of the underground cables. This can

accelerate the aging of the components and lead to abrupt cable failures [14]. This indicates that the proximity to roads can have an impact on the failure probability of the DS components and thus should be considered.

Distance to DC railways: The running rails of a DC train-system are typically used as a return conductor for traction current. Due to the low resistance between the traction return rails and the surface, a significant amount of the return current can leak into the ground. This current can create or accelerate the electrolytic corrosion of metallic constructions alongside the railway [10]. This could potentially be a problem for lead cover cables (PILC cables) as there is generally good electric contact between the lead sheath and ground.

DEFINITION OF DATA SOURCES

National fault and outage statistics of Denmark

In the national fault and outage statistics of Denmark (ELFAS) operated by Green Power Denmark, Danish DSOs have been recording faults and interruptions of medium voltage components since 1974. The ELFAS database includes all faults that have led to a customer being disconnected. The available parameters are, but not limited to: failure date [date] and cause [category], component category [kV], interrupted customers [number] and time [minutes], voltage level of component [kV], company [id], disconnected components [ids].

Data provided by Danish DSOs

Several of the required data, such as root data, electrical parameters, date of components installation and end of life, and GIS Locations of grid components, are not publicly available, but are owned by DSOs. For this study, several Danish DSOs shared relevant cable root, GIS, and installation age data. In this way the following parameters, among others, were collected: asset unique ID [id], cable type [category], length [m], in-service date [date], year of manufacture [year], manufacturer [category], model [category], design voltage [kV], operating voltage [kV], GIS coordinates [Long, Lat], max loading [%].

Public sources

Many of the mentioned location-based features are publicly available and distributed via public services, such as the “Danish Agency for Data Supply and Infrastructure” (<https://sdfi.dk/>, 17.01.23). So, there are several INSPIRE Datasets available, providing parameters such as: railways [GIS], roads [GIS], train type, road type, land use [category] and wetland areas [GIS].

Furthermore, the “Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI)” (<https://www.dmi.dk>, 17.01.23) provides large amounts of climate and lightning data and parameters such as: mean, min, max temperature [°C], pressure [hPa], relative humidity [%], wind speed [m/s], number of ice days, location of lightning [GIS], number of lightning strokes, lightning strength [kA]. In addition, the Hydrological Altitude Model offers further hydrological information, such as where water would flow in the event of extreme rainfall, which areas will be flooded at a given sea level or where

there will be flooding from in storm surge or other sea water rise (<https://dataforsyningen.dk/data/2695>, 17.01.23). Lastly, the "The Danish Register of Underground Cable Owners (LER)" saves information about current and previous digging activities in Denmark and provided the following parameters to this study: digging area [GIS], start-time and end-time [datetime], industry and digging type [category] (<https://graveinfo.ler.dk/>, 17.01.23).

Figure 2: The distance to DC railways in [m] as one feature to represent accelerated aging of MV cables

CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

Data collection

Although a high degree of features has been collected, difficulties in the data collection process were revealed. One barrier was for example, that many stakeholders were involved. Thus, there is no single point of contact, and the data needs to be requested and shared multiple times. Consequently, multiple data sharing and confidentiality agreements are needed, as some data contains information about critical infrastructure. This result in administrative issues. Future studies should therefore prioritise the features and sources that are easiest to access and standardize data sharing processes between the different stakeholders. Furthermore, due to different sources, data often comes in different types and formats, which also leads to high data collecting efforts, as merging of the data is another big task.

Data availability and quality

The provided data does not always meet desired data completeness requirements especially for features such as, in-service date [date], year of manufacture [year], electrical parameters or information about previous discarded and failed components. This is because, data owner themselves often face data availability issues. Therefore, a strong need for the application of data enrichment strategies was identified.

The main issue for publicly available features, such as climate, soil type or land use data, is that it remains uncertain if the provided resolution or granularity is high enough for a detailed reliability assessment.

Furthermore, only a limited number of electrical parameters and measurement readings were shared. One barrier is that smart meter readings are available but often not prepared and aggregated in a format that can be linked to MV cables.

In this behalf, privacy concerns need to be overcome through virtualisation and anonymisation of the data. As pointed out, the location of failures is highly relevant for reliability studies of MV cables. However, the GIS coordinates of failures in ELFAS are in most cases not tracked. This applies to failures prior to 2018 and necessitates the use of estimation techniques for failure localisation.

Data transformation

The main purpose for redefining data requirements for the reliability assessment of medium voltage lies in their usage for ML based condition monitoring and predictive maintenance applications. These require a combined and pre-processed dataset. Some operational features, such as distance to roads (see Figure 2), can be easily derived from cable location and publicly available information. Other features require further calculations or assumptions, e.g., impact through digging activities or lightning.

Issues in the data transformation arise if two datasets cannot be merged directly. Then mapping strategies, such as rule-based, Fuzzy, K-nearest neighbour or supervised learning techniques need to be applied. For the presented sources this was especially the case for cable root data and failure reports, as a unique cable identifier linking failure reports to currently or previously used cables was mostly not available.

Different data timeframes present another challenge, as here synthetic data creation, categorisation or simulation based on the raw data might become necessary.

DISCUSSION

This report proposes the collection and combination of several data features to model reliability of MV cables. However, it does not provide an evaluation of their value contribution to the reliability model development.

This underlines that an investigation of the relationship between data requirements, collection, availability, quality as well as benefit for condition monitoring and predictive maintenance application needs to be tackled by further studies. The application of established feature selection methods based on statistics will be required in this behalf. As an output the required quantity, quality, and granularity of data, as well as the cost of measuring and collection should be defined. So, recommendations can be given, which data sources provide the highest value to the distribution system operators. In this way the knowledge on which feature to prioritize will eventually also facilitate the optimization of data collection process for reliability assessment within DSOs.

Another remaining issue is that many of the presented features are available as a snapshot. Thus, future work needs to include strategies to automatically update and manage required data. Moreover, features described in this paper represent only a subset of possible drivers to consider.

To broaden the investigation, consideration of more features, e.g., maintenance efforts, power quality measurements, harmonics, smart meter data, renewable generation, or electric vehicles, could be of potential interest as well.

Besides, no sources for cable temperature data have been identified so far. Therefore, it could be of interest to use temperature estimation algorithms based on industrial standards to calculate temperatures, based on operational and environmental conditions. Another option would be the integration of additional IoT sensor data (e.g., partial discharge measurement).

This paper highlights difficulties in the availability of measurement readings in DSs, such as aggregated smart meter data. This also underlines the importance of intelligent estimation algorithms. Moreover, could the dataset be enlarged to consider more DS components, like high voltage and extra high voltage switchgears, joints, or low voltage boards. In this behalf system reliability studies could be fulfilled based on the estimated failure probabilities. Future studies should also investigate how the data requirements and collection could be standardised and scaled for different stakeholders, based on for example virtualisation strategies.

Once the data requirements are fulfilled, the development and application of ML based reliability models for MV cables will be possible. This will enable the comparison with existing reliability model approaches, for example the CNAIM [12]. Furthermore, will data driven models benefit the development of optimal sensor placement strategies, such as partial discharge measurement.

CONCLUSION

This study underlines that ML based reliability assessment of MV cables lacks uniform data. Thus, it emphasises the need for a re-definition of data requirements, as well as data collection, management, and combination processes. Consequently, this work firstly lists main data features to represent failure and aging driver of MV cables, explaining their relevance and relation to ageing mechanisms. Thereafter, the authors outline main sources for the defined features for Denmark and identify issues, such as high administrative efforts in the collection process relating to the high number of stakeholders involved, as well as data availability and quality issues. To use the collected features for ML based models they need to be combined. Therefore, this paper highlights main data mapping challenges, such the linkage of failure reports, component data and location-based features as well as required efforts for the alignment of different data types and timeframes.

The paper closes with a discussion on objectives for future studies. In conclusion, future research should evaluate the value contribution of each collected features within the reliability modelling, and specify their optimal quantity, quality and granularity. New data sources and features (e.g., based on IoT sensors) should be integrated stepwise and the value contribution of all features should be re-evaluated accordingly. Lastly, data requirements and sharing processes should be standardised and DSOs data collection efforts be optimised.

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